

SOME CHARACTERISTICS OF TRANSPIRATION OF PROMISING SOYBEAN'S VARIETIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8251330>

Annotation. The article presents data obtained from the study of the daily intensity of transpiration during the flowering stage of soybean varieties. According to the data on the diurnal variation of transpiration intensity, this process was accelerated in Vilana and Ustoz MM-60 varieties of soybeans, and a relative decrease in intensity was observed in Baraka and Tomaris man-60 varieties. Different variations in the intensity of transpiration in the cross section of the studied varieties may depend on the biological characteristics of the varieties as well as the air temperature and its relative humidity level.

Keywords: Soybean varieties, transpiration rate, temperature, humidity, water exchange, productivity.

Introduction. Water is a major part of plants and they play an important role in life activities. The role of water in plant life is extremely important, as 70-95% of the composition of plant tissues consists of water, the amount of which in the seeds decreases sharply and ranges from 5 to 15%. Water is the main mass in all organs of the plant: 90% in the leaf, 70-80% in the branch, 50-60% in the root, 10% in the seed, 98% in the vacuole, 80% in the cytoplasm, 50% in the bark. Some wet fruits contain a lot of water: tomatoes - up to 94%, watermelons - up to 92% [1].

To increase plant biomass to 1 gram, approximately 500 g of water must be absorbed by the root system, assimilated by the plant, and released into the atmosphere from the surface of its vegetative organs. Due to its unique properties, water is of great importance in all processes of cell life. Even a slight violation of the water regime causes significant changes in metabolic processes [2].

It is known that transpiration is one of the most important and necessary physiological processes in plants, protecting plants from overheating and dehydration in dry and hot weather, as well as the movement of water and water-soluble substances throughout the plant body, gas exchange [3]. The temperature of a highly transpired leaf is about 7 °C lower than that of a non-transpired withered leaf [4].

The water consumption of a plant for transpiration is mainly determined by solar energy and soil moisture. The intensity of transpiration varies depending on the time of year and day, meteorological conditions, biological properties of plants, cultivation technology and other factors [5].

It is known that transpiration in leaves is one of the important physiological processes, especially in the study of plant growth and development in areas where water scarcity is observed. Transpiration ensures not only the evaporation of water through the leaf, but also the adsorption of water and the movement of water and dissolved substances throughout the plant [6].

The water supply activity of plants is directly related to the intensity of transpiration. 0.2% of the water taken in by the plants is assimilated and the rest is evaporated through the leaves during transpiration. In determining the nature of the water balance in plants, it is also important to determine the rate of water consumption depending on environmental factors. An increase in water scarcity in the soil leads to a decrease in transpiration intensity. Otherwise, the inverse law is observed [7].

In plants with moderate humidity, the total amount of water was found to fluctuate throughout the day. This is inextricably linked to the intensity of transpiration. Depending on the amount of water consumed during transpiration, it is possible to determine the water requirements and needs of a particular plant. A number of factors need to be considered when determining the amount of water used for transpiration. These include the mass and volume of the root system, the mass of the plant surface organs, the osmotic pressure of the stem cell sap, depth of groundwater, amount of precipitation, air temperature and relative humidity, soil moisture reserve, the value of water potential of plants, etc. The intensity of transpiration determines the condition of the mouthparts and the amount of water in the leaves as well as the level of water supply to the plants. In some cases, as a result of rapid dehydration of the leaves, the mouthpieces become unable to control water consumption. As a result, the photosynthetic activity of the leaves decreases [8].

Accelerated transpiration in conditions of water scarcity leads to the appearance of water deficiency in the body of plants. As a result, plant growth and productivity are reduced. Under such conditions, the use of transpiration is recommended to prevent water loss by plants [9].

Under conditions of sufficient water, open mouths characterize the resistance of plants to atmospheric drought. At the same time, transpiration is accelerated, which strongly protects plants from water shortages.

When there is a lack of water, the pores close and the level of turgor and transpiration of the leaves decreases, including photosynthesis. As a result, overall productivity decreases. The productivity of drought-tolerant plants was higher than that of drought-tolerant ones [10,11].

Based on the above data, we studied the intensity of transpiration during the flowering phase of promising soybean varieties.

Object and methods of research. The research was conducted at the Surkhandarya Scientific Experimental Station of the Scientific Research Institute of Cotton Breeding, Seed Production and Agrotechnology. 4 promising soybean varieties (local Baraka, Tomaris man-60, Ustoz MM-60 and foreign Vilana) were used as the object of development. Experimental experiments were carried out in field conditions on four rotating, 15m² plots. The number of sown seeds was 350,000 per hectare, and sowing was carried out using pneumatic seeders. Placement of experimental plots was carried out according to the method of B.A. Dospekhov[12]. Crop care was carried out in accordance with the measures recommended in the region.

The transpiration intensity of soybean leaves was determined by the method of rapid pulling on a torsion balance (L.A. Ivanov method)[13]. Determination of transpiration intensity was performed on the basis of three repetitions from 8 a.m. to 8 p.m. Mathematical and statistical processing of the obtained experimental data was carried out using modern computer programs.

Research results and its discussion. In the early stages of growth, evaporation from the soil surface predominates, after which most of the water is assimilated by plants for transpiration. The soybean consumed during the flowering, legume formation and ripening stages accounted for 60-70% of the water consumed during the entire growing season. Violation of the water regime during this period leads to the shedding of buds, flowers and fruits, especially in the period of gross flowering drought leads to a decrease in soybean yield by 50% or more.

According to information scientists, transpiration rates are lower in drought-tolerant varieties than in non-drought-tolerant varieties. Increased water supply to plants also increases water consumption through transpiration. Lack of water in the soil reduces the rate of transpiration in plants. In plants with moderate humidity, transpiration rates are higher than in water-deficient environments, and transpiration productivity is also higher [14].

Studies have shown that the intensity of transpiration of soybean leaves depends significantly on the phases of plant development, with development

being maximized during the period of formation of generative organs, i.e., periods of gross flowering and fruiting (Table 1).

Table 1.

Daily variation of transpiration intensity in leaves of different soybean varieties, g/m² h

		8:00	10:00	12:00	14:00	16:00	18:00	20:00	Average
№	Air temperature, °C	26 °C	32 °C	34 °C	36 °C	37 °C	36 °C	30 °C	33°C
	Air humidity, %	27 %	20 %	14 %	10 %	9 %	14 %	17 %	16%
1	Baraka	82,6	114,3	140,6	162,6	189,3	126,2	115,2	132,97
2	<u>Tomaris</u> man-60	57,6	100,6	125,8	146,5	164,8	118,2	98,5	116,0
3	<u>Ustoz</u> MM- 60	78,5	110,5	133,4	158,4	171,6	120,7	108,4	141,45
4	<u>Vilana</u>	86,4	125,4	168,9	177,3	197,4	136,5	125,8	145,38

In contrast to other crops in the shade plant, the plant is characterized by long flowering and ripening of legumes. From the data obtained, it was observed that the transpiration intensity of soybean varieties varies depending on the variety characteristics and air temperature. In all shade varieties studied, transpiration rates were low in the morning, highest in the afternoon, and low again in the evening.

According to the data obtained, 145.38 grams of water evaporated in 1 hour at the level of 1 m² of leaves of Vilana variety, while 116 grams of water evaporated from the leaves of Tomaris man-60 variety during this period, that is, during this period, Vilana evaporated 29.38 grams less water than Tomaris man-60 navigator. The remaining varieties also took intermediate positions, evaporating less water than the Vilana navigator, that is, Baraka variety

evaporated 12.41 grams, Master MM-60 variety evaporated 3.93 g less water. It was noted that this indicator differs sharply from each other in terms of transpiration intensity of varieties.

As the level of water supply increases, so does the rate of transpiration and water consumption of plants. Decreasing the soil moisture level from optimal to minimum sharply reduces the transpiration rate, resulting in reduced plant growth and productivity [15,16].

Conclusion. Thus, the research conducted is the basis for our conclusion in soybean crops as well as in other agricultural crops. The transpiration intensity of the studied varieties was mainly directly related to the location of the leaves on the plant, the time of day, the increase in temperature, and the relative humidity.

The maximum point of the curve representing the intensity of transpiration occurred in all varieties between 14-16 hours. The intensity of transpiration in the leaves of local varieties of shade was 189.3 in Baraka variety at 1400-1600 hours; 164.8 in Tomaris man-60 variety; Teacher MM-60 navida 171.6; in the foreign Vilana variety 197.4 g/m² h, minimum at 800 in the morning: 82.6, respectively; 57.6; 78.5 and 86.4 g/m² per hour.

References:

1. Вавилов П.П. Ўсимликшунослик. –Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 1980.- 630 б.
2. Медведев С.С. Физиология растений Изд-во С.-Петербур. ун-та, 2004.-336 с.
3. Kholliye, A, Norboyeva, U, & Adizova, K (2020). About the negative impact of salination on cotton. Збірник наукових праць Л'ОГОС, 50-52
4. Малиновский В. И. Физиология растений.-Владивосток, 2004.-382 с.
5. Toshtemirovna, NU, & Ergashovich, KA (2019). Physiology, productivity and cotton plant adaptation under the conditions of soil salinity. International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering 8 (2 S3), 1611-1613
6. Toshtemirovna, NU, & Ergashovich, KA (2019). Regulation of the water balance of the cotton varieties under salting conditions. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 9(8), 5-9
7. Shah N.H., Paulsen G.M. Interaction of drought and high temperature on photosynthesis and grain-filling of wheat // Plant Soil. 2003. – V. 257. – P. 219-226.
8. Хўжаев Ж.Х. Маданий экинлар ҳосилдорлигини оширишнинг биологик асослари // Ўзбекистон флораси биохилма-хиллиги ва ундан оқилона фойдаланиш муаммолари: Республика илмий-амалий конф. материаллари. – Самарқанд, 2011. –Б. 69-72.

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9. Toshtemirovna, NU, & Ergashovich, KA (2019). Regulation of the water balance of the cotton varieties under salting conditions. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(8), 5-9
10. Ergashovich, KA, Azamatovna, BZ, Toshtemirovna, NU, & Rakhimovna, AK (2020). Ecophysiological effects of water deficiency on cotton varieties. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(9), 244-246
11. Kholliyev, A, & Boltayeva, Z (2020). Resistance of cotton varieties to water deficiency. *Збірник наукових праць Л'ОГОС*, 70-72
12. Доспехов Б.А. Методика полевого опыта. – М., Агропромиздат, 1985. – 347с
13. Иванов Л.А., Силина А.А., Цельникер Ю.Л. О методике быстрого взвешивания для определения транспирации в естественных условиях // *Ботан. Журнал*. 1950. Т. 35. № 2. С. 171-185.
14. Baloch M.J., Khan N.U., Jatoi W.A., Hassan G., Khakhwani A.A., Soomro Z.A., Veesar N.F. Drought tolerance studies through WSSI and stomata in upland cotton // *Pak. J. Bot.* 2011. – V. 43. – P. 2479-2484.
15. Kholliyev, A, Boltayeva, Z, & Norboyeva, U (2020). Cotton water exchange in water deficiency. *Збірник наукових праць Л'ОГОС*, 54-56
16. Kholliyev, A, Norboyeva, U, & Adizova, K (2020). Methods of using microelements to increase salt resistance of cotton. *Збірник наукових праць Л'ОГОС*, 57-60
17. A.E., NUT Kholliyev, & F.I., Nazarova (2021). Cotton resistance Indicators in the Conditions of Water deficiency. *The riving force of science and trends in its development*, 3, 7-9
18. Ergashovich, KA, Toshtemirovna, NU, Rakhimovna, AK, & Abdullayevna, FF (2020). Effects of Microelements on Drought Resistance of Cotton Plant. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(2)

